

Electrochemical preparation of graphene quantum dots from wood charcoal as a peroxidase mimetic

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Abstract

Horseshoe peroxidase (HRP) has been extensively used in enzyme linked sorbent assay (ELISA) based disease diagnosis. Like other natural enzymes, the expensive steps involved in the production of HRP along with its extreme environmental sensitivity, limits its potential applications. To overcome these challenges considerable efforts have been made to explore HRP activity of nanomaterials. In present study, we highlight electrochemical synthesis of nearly uniform size (~ 5 nm) of graphene quantum dots (E-GQDs) from wood charcoal and their further application as colorimetric detection of H₂O₂ and glucose. E-GQDs allowed a rapid and sensitive detection of glucose with a detection limit of 0.006 mM for dynamic response range of 0.01–0.6 mM. Study introduces a cheap and widely available raw material for the electrochemical synthesis of graphene quantum dots with commendable enzyme mimetic activity which may have a huge impact in developing colorimetric bioanalysis systems.

Figure: Time-dependent absorbance changes at 652 nm of TMB solution in different reaction systems

Keywords: E-GQDs, Horse radish peroxidase (HRP), Glucose oxidase (GOx), Colorimetric, Peroxidase mimetic

Reference

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